

BorderForce

Flexible system extending automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events

D1.2 – Project Data Management Plan (PDMP)

WP1 - Project Management – Prototype in Industrial Environment

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Publishable Executive Summary

This deliverable constitutes the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the BorderForce project, outlining the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the whole Consortium. The DMP gives a general outline of the rights and the integrity of all generated/processed/collected data as well as the procedures that will be followed to acquire the data with respect to their sensitivity and the measures that need to be followed throughout this process. In that way, the DMP presents how research data will be handled during the BorderForce project, and even after the project is completed, describes what data, methodology and standards will be followed, and whether this data will be shared and/or made open. Moreover, only public information has been provided in this document, thus for a more detailed understanding of specific procedures needed to handle specific data in the project, other documents have been provided in the context of BorderForce, such as a number of provisions on Ethical aspects fulfilling ethical requirements.

The present deliverable constitutes the Project Data Management Plan at Month 6 of the project. The described data management policy reflects the current state of Consortium agreements regarding data management and is consistent with those referring to the exploitation and protection of results and can also be considered as a checklist for the future. Moreover, the different aspects of making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR) are presented.

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List of Abbreviations

Term	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EPC	Grant of European Patents
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	intellectual Property Rights
PDMP	Project Data Management Plan

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

This deliverable aims to provide an extensive analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the participants of the BorderForce project with regard to all the datasets that the project will generate. It describes the data management life cycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed, or generated by the BorderForce project. This deliverable presents how data will be handled during and even after the project is completed, describing:

- the data,
- implemented methodology and standards,
- data sharing and open access practices,
- data curation and preservation practices

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 outlines the fundamental guidelines for data management and the corresponding legal framework
- Section 3 describes, among others, the purposes of data collection or generation, the types and formats of collected or generated data, data origin, expected data size, and access levels.
- Section 4 presents the FAIR (Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable) principles that guide the project's data management.
- Section 5 describes the allocation of resources, including the costs of implementing the FAIR principles and how the costs will be covered throughout the whole period of the project.
- Section 6 outlines the provisions which are implemented for data security and safe storage (partners' repository or database) to preserve and curate the data.
- Section 7 outlines the types of personal data which will be processed in the scope of the project.
- Section 8 describes the management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).
- Section 9 outlines the ethical and legal aspects that may influence data sharing, including references to ethics deliverables and the ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Section 10 concludes this deliverable

2 GUIDELINES OF DATA MANAGEMENT AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK

BorderForce will design data collection processes that adhere to the principles of data protection, striving for data minimisation and anonymisation whenever possible in terms of Data Protection and impact of the research on fundamental rights and values.

In compliance with the above, the relevant legislation listed below shall be considered:

- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (2000/c 364/01)
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679);
- Convention No. 108 of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals about Automatic Processing of Personal Data adopted on 28 January 1997.
- Recommendation No. R (97) 18 of the Committee of Ministers to Member States concerning the protection of personal data collected and processed for statistical purposes, adopted on 30 September 1997.
- Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases.
- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications).

2.1 Definitions and Data Protection Principles (GDPR)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679) applies to all personal data processed in the BorderForce project. Personal data is defined in Article 4(1) as any information relating to an identified or identifiable individual, including names, voice recordings, images, or location data.

In the context of BorderForce:

- A data subject (Article 4 (1)) is an identifiable person whose an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person. These subjects have the right to exercise their rights under GDPR Articles 13 to 22. These rights include the right to access, rectify, delete, restrict, and object to the processing of their data, as well as the right to data portability.
- A data controller (Article 4(7)) determines the purposes and means of processing (e.g. partner conducting interviews).
- A data processor (Article 4(8)) processes data on behalf of the controller (e.g. platform host).

These roles must be clearly defined in each work package involving personal data.

2.2 Key GDPR Principles Applicable to BorderForce:

- **Lawfulness, fairness, and transparency (Article 5(1)(a)):** Personal data must be collected and used in a legal and transparent way. Participants must be clearly

informed when their data is processed, especially during interviews, workshops, or field trials.

- **Purpose limitation (Article 5(1)(b)):** Data must only be collected for specific, explicit purposes (e.g. developing user requirements or training modules), and not repurposed without further consent.
- **Data minimisation (Article 5(1)(c)):** Only data strictly necessary for achieving the task's objective should be collected. For example, anonymised workshop summaries may be sufficient instead of full transcripts.
- **Accuracy (Articles 5(1)(d) and 16):** Personal data must be kept accurate and up to date. Participants have the right to request corrections or deletion of incorrect data.
- **Storage limitation (Article 5(1)(e)):** Personal data must not be kept longer than necessary. Each partner must define retention periods based on the purpose of the processing.
- **Integrity and confidentiality (Article 5(1)(f)):** Data must be protected from unauthorised access or loss using appropriate technical and organisational measures (e.g. encryption, access controls).

2.3 Pseudonymisation and Anonymisation

In line with Article 89 and Recital 26, partners must apply pseudonymisation or anonymisation where possible. Anonymised data falls outside GDPR scope, but pseudonymised data must still be protected. Before dissemination or reuse (e.g. scientific purposes), personal data must be anonymised unless explicit consent is obtained.

2.4 Data Handling Obligations

Partners are required to comply with the following GDPR obligations:

- **Article 25 – Data protection by design and by default:** Partners must implement technical and organizational measures that ensure personal data is processed in accordance with GDPR principles from the outset of any activity, and that, by default, only the necessary personal data for each specific purpose is collected and processed.
- **Article 30 – Records of processing activities:** Each partner must maintain detailed and up-to-date records of all processing activities involving personal data, which must be made available to supervisory authorities upon request.
- **Article 32 – Security of processing, including encryption and secure storage:** Partners must ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of personal data through appropriate technical and organizational security measures, including encryption, access controls, secure storage, and protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction, or damage

Additionally, any transfers of data to non-EU partners (e.g. in Albania or Moldova) must follow the requirements for international transfers under GDPR, with safeguards in place to ensure that data subjects are fully protected in accordance with European data protection standards.

3 DATA SUMMARY

3.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation and relation to the objectives of BorderForce

Data collection, generation, and processing are essential for achieving the objectives of BorderForce. These activities support research, system design, and validation efforts across all work packages. The types of data include both non-personal and potentially personal data. Where personal or sensitive data is involved, the project will apply appropriate ethical safeguards in line with the GDPR, the AI Act, and the Horizon Europe ethics framework. The purpose is described as follows:

- Data exploited for research purposes in creating deliverables in almost all WPs through desktop research and literature review, interviews, and workshops in the form of recordings, written notes, and transcripts.
- Data exploited for research purposes in WP2 in the framework of identifying the end-user requirements, training scenarios, and the development of a comprehensive perspective on border surveillance, situational awareness, and authorities’ response mechanisms to different incidents, including an in-depth analysis of various social and organisational processes, work practices, user roles, and operational environments.
- Data regarding the development of the BorderForce components in WP3, WP4 and WP8.
- Data regarding the integration of all components into the BorderForce Platform in WP5.
- Data extracted from the field trials in WP9

3.2 Types and formats of data that BorderForce will generate/collect

In order to fulfil the purpose of the data collection/generation, the BorderForce project will collect and generate the following types and formats of data:

Data/Data Source	Data type	Data format	Data origin
Surveys, workshops/field test data, validation cycles data	Electronic document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word document (.doc,.docx) • Excel document (.xls/.xlsx) • Pdf document 	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP8, WP9, WP10
	Hardcopy	paper	
Deliverables	Electronic document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word document (.doc,.docx) • Excel document (.xls/.xlsx) • Pdf document 	All WPs
	Hardcopy	paper	

Website public reports	Electronic document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word document (.doc/.docx) • Pdf document • Excel document (.xls/.xlsx) • .csv files • .txt 	All WPs
Video files	Electronic document	.mov, .mpeg, .avi, .mp4, etc.	All WPs
Audio files	Electronic document	.mp3, .wav, etc.	All WPs
Images	Electronic document	.jpg, .png, .gif, etc.	All WPs
Software	Source Code	Source Code	WP3, WP4, WP8
Signed documents (eg. Consent forms, information sheets, attendance lists, Consortium Agreement, etc.)	Electronic document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word document (.doc,.docx) • Excel document (.xls/.xlsx) • Pdf document 	WP1, WP2, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP9, WP10
	Hardcopy	paper	
Presentations	Electronic document	PowerPoint document	All WPs
	Hardcopy	paper	

Table 1 Types and formats of data

3.3 Information types in the BorderForce project

Following the “Guidance Guidelines for the classification of research results” of the European Commission, the deliverables have two types of classification: PUBLIC, SENSITIVE

3.3.1 Public

In Table 2, BorderForce deliverables which are classified as PUBLIC are shown.

No	Deliverable	Deliverable Title
1	D1.1	Project Quality Management Plan (PQMP)
2	D1.2	Project Data Management Plan (PDMP)
3	D1.3	Ethics assessment and Innovation Management
4	D2.4	AI Act Compliance Report, PIA, EIA, and SIA assessments
5	D6.1	Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan
6	D6.2	Initial Communication, Dissemination, Advisory Board Activities and Exploitation/Standardisation Plan
7	D7.1	Innovation and Management Activities
8	D9.2	Ethics Training and Monitoring Activities
9	D9.3	Assessment, Evaluation and Lessons Learned in Operational Environment
10	D9.4	Field Trials in Operational Environment - Public
11	D10.1	Communication, Dissemination and Advisory Board Activities

12	D10.2	Exploitation, Standardisation and Industrial Showcase Activities
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Table 2 Public Deliverables

3.3.2 Sensitive

In Table 3, BorderForce deliverables which are classified as SENSITIVE are shown.

No	Deliverable	Deliverable Title
1	D2.1	User Requirements and System Architecture (1st Version)
2	D2.2	User Requirements and System Architecture (2nd Version)
3	D2.3	Pilot Use Case Definition and Assessment Methodology
4	D3.1	BorderForce Monitoring Capabilities
5	D4.1	BorderForce System Intelligence and Situational Awareness Capabilities
6	D5.1	System Integration in Industrial Environment, Introduction to XR/MR Capabilities
7	D5.2	Performance Evaluation, Benchmarking and Lessons Learned in Industrial Environment
8	D8.1	BorderForce Operational Environment Platform Integration and Test
9	D9.1	Field Trials in Operational Environment

Table 3 Sensitive Deliverables

3.4 Origin of the data, reuse of existing ones and expected size of the data

Existing research and personal data is not foreseen to be used or merged for the purposes of the BorderForce project.

To support the project deliverables, data will be collected, evaluated, and aggregated from end-users and external stakeholders engaged in the project activities, acquired through desktop research, workshops and surveys. Potential existing data will be exploited in the form of published materials relating to border security and serve as a reference in order to analyse operational or other incidents that may occur.

To support the development of the BorderForce components, data from various sensors (cameras, satellites, etc) will be used.

The expected size of the data collected/generated/processed under the BorderForce project ranges from kilobytes to gigabytes, even terabytes, depending on the period of retention of the data, the sensor data, and the transcripts of the surveys.

3.5 Usefulness of collected data

The data generated in the project will be highly valuable to a diverse range of stakeholders, including policymakers, research institutions, and technology providers engaged in the border management domain. Policymakers can utilize this data to develop evidence-based strategies, improve regulatory frameworks, and enhance decision-making processes

related to border management. Research institutions can leverage the insights to conduct in-depth analyses, assess emerging trends, and propose innovative solutions to address challenges in border control and surveillance. Technology providers, on the other hand, can use the data to refine existing solutions ultimately improving the efficiency and effectiveness of border security operations. Additionally, the data may support law enforcement agencies, international organizations, and customs authorities by providing valuable intelligence to streamline operations, enhance risk assessment, and strengthen cross-border cooperation.

4 FAIR DATA

According to the Guidelines for the Classification of Information in Research Project the research data must be findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable. These principles precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation solution. Nevertheless, for the duration of the BorderForce project, partners will work under these guidelines maintaining adherence to the classification of information stated above. In the following, the approach of the BorderForce project to each FAIR principle is addressed within dedicated sub-sections.

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Storage, processing and sharing (among project participants) will be supported via a dedicated data sharing platform, whereas interaction with the wider public will be achieved through the official project website. Data will be stored and will be kept for 5 years after the end of the project.

The data from the surveys, workshops/demonstrations, and the validation cycles will not be published as primary data (data that is collected directly from the data source) due to privacy and security concerns.

BorderForce project complies with the principal priorities as defined below:

- The publications will be made available through the project's website, and the data produced will be discoverable with metadata and identifiable and locatable by the Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). The metadata will include: title, data types/formats and software, data collection method and dates, geographic coverage, language, data processing details, funding details, ethics clearance details, a project abstract, keywords, and licensing.
- Data needed for the collaborative tools are expected to include a unique ID and a timestamp allowing for proper indexing and handling when stored. No specific standards or metadata have been identified for the time being for the datasets.
- The data from the surveys, workshops/living labs, and the validation cycles will not be published as primary data (data that is collected directly from the data source) due to privacy and security concerns.

4.2 Making data openly accessible

All publications will be made available through ArXiv (<https://arxiv.org/>) repository or OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>).

Additionally, the interview data (recordings, protocols, and transcriptions) from experts will not be made openly available and will not be published as primary data due to privacy and security concerns. Anonymization is not considered as an alternative, because the limited number of the interviews allows for drawing conclusions on the respondents, increasing the risk of re-identification. Selected anonymous results could be used for publishing academic papers on border security training needs.

4.2.1 Data produced or collected made accessible

Access to the data will be controlled through strict and secure authentication and authorization services, supported by role-based access control, thus ensuring that only authenticated and authorized users can access the stored information.

The data from the surveys will not be accessible by all consortium partners as primary data due to privacy and security concerns.

4.3 Making data interoperable

The concept of interoperability demands that both data and metadata must be machine-readable and that a consistent terminology is used. To that extent, a specific document template (XML, JSON, etc) describing the structure of the exchanged information will be used.

4.3.1 Standard vocabulary

In almost all cases, the vocabulary used will be standard for all data types and make use of a common language within the business creation culture. Vocabulary won't represent any barrier to data interoperability and re-use.

4.4 Increase data re-use

The re-use of data (if needed) will be restricted to the research use of the license and anonymous data can be used for scientific publications. Data may not be copied or distributed and must be referenced if used in publications. The collected data will be a consolidation of data from several sources, each one having its own policies.

Use of Creative Commons licenses, the default being CC-BY 4.0, which makes data very widely re-usable shall be encouraged for research articles, allowing copying, distribution, and transmission of work without affecting essential author rights.

5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

The costs of making data FAIR have been allocated and covered by the BorderForce project budget. Thus, it is foreseen at this point that no extra costs will be incurred. The dissemination material (e.g. scientific publications) will be made available through ArXiv or OpenAIRE with no additional costs if possible.

In general, the person responsible for data management and compliance regarding the BorderForce project is the Data Protection Officer (DPO), as well as the contact point and DPOs of each organisation.

6 DATA SECURITY

The data collected/generated throughout the whole period of the BorderForce project will be held in data repositories in the servers of organisations. The servers will be kept in locked rooms with authorized access and will adhere to appropriate security standards as well as to state-of-the art security mechanisms. The data repositories will be accessed by authorized personnel both at physical and network levels. The databases will have a dedicated identification and authentication mechanism, name and password, for each authorized user and will adhere to different access privileges for the authorized users of the organisation in any case.

Access to the data repository will be achieved through the appropriate protocols. The transfer of the data (e.g. files, deliverables, raw data etc.) will be achieved using encryption methods (e.g. file transfers, encrypted disks, encryption keys, a physically protected and secure PC responsible for this process) when necessary.

As for the "physical" data storage, the documents will be kept in an office's secure environment, in computers with authentication and authorization mechanisms. If there are documents with restricted access, they will remain in a locked cabinet at the organisation's premises.

Backups of the databases will be stored encrypted and on the organisations' premises. Data backups of devices will happen every week and be stored in devices that follow the same security standards and procedures as the main server

7 PERSONAL DATA MANAGEMENT

Article 1 of the European Parliament and Council Regulation on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR), describes data protection as both a central issue for research ethics in Europe and a fundamental human right. As such, BorderForce is committed to ensuring that protection of personal data is robustly respected and protected during the course of the project.

This Section will outline BorderForce’s activities in relating to the following; (a) personal data and special categories of data that are used (b) the processing of personal data and the lawful basis for such, and (c) the adherence to key principles such as data minimisation, purpose limitation, and security.

7.1 Definition of personal data

Personal data is defined in Article 4(1) of the GDPR as:

“...any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”.

7.2 Processing of personal data

As outlined in Article 15 of the GA, beneficiaries must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection, in particular the GDPR. Further, the GA notes that all of the data processed will be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary (data minimisation principle), to achieve the goals of the project. The below will outline BorderForce’s purpose, the scope of the data processed in view of the project’s purpose, and lastly, the implementation of the data minimisation principle while achieving this purpose.

7.2.1 Scope of data processing in BorderForce

Processing of personal data is defined by Article 4(2) GDPR as:

“any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction;”

Article 5 GDPR, provides the principles relating to the processing of personal data and are as follows:

“ 1. Personal data shall be:

- a) processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject (‘lawfulness, fairness and transparency’);

- b) collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation');
- c) adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimisation');
- d) accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay ('accuracy');
- e) kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed; personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this Regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject ('storage limitation');
- f) processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures ('integrity and confidentiality').

1. The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with, paragraph 1 ('accountability')."

The principles relating to processing personal data were also explicitly outlined in Article 15 on data protection in the BorderForce GA. In line with the GDPR's requirements in Article 5, by signing the GA, partners have committed to ensuring personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.

Lawfulness of processing is outlined in Article 6(1) GDPR and is as follows:

1. "Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies:

- a) the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes;
- b) processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;
- c) processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject;
- d) processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;
- e) processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller;
- f) processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.

Point (f) of the first subparagraph shall not apply to processing carried out by public authorities in the performance of their tasks.”

Relating to the lawfulness of processing it is the responsibility of the partners processing the personal data to clearly identify the legal basis on which they process data.

Briefly, as shown in the Table below, the legal basis for collection and processing of any personal data which is required for research activities is premised on Article 6(1)(b) GDPR, is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party in addition to the consent of participants, as per Article 6 (1)(a) GDPR, and Recital 39 GDPR. The legal basis for dissemination activities is the legitimate interest of the partners, as per Article 6(1)(f) GDPR, and those people contacted based on the legitimate interests of the BorderForce partners can opt out from these communications at any time through an ‘unsubscribe’ button. However, the Table below contains a task by task identification of the legal basis for processing personal data.

Task	Personal data categories	Data subject categories	Processing Purposes	Legal Basis for processing	Transfer of personal data to non-EU or non-EEA country
Task 1.1-T1.5	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organisation	Consortium Partners	For the purpose of communication, cooperation and information sharing between Consortium Partners.	Article 6(1)(b): performance of a contract: Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)

				validation under the Grant Agreement	
Task 2.1	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organisation. Country of organisation in which the end user is employed, their organisation, and organisational unit	External stakeholders (Border management authorities other than project partners, CSDP entities other than project partners)	VTT will identify and recruit external stakeholders to conduct interviews to support the Concept of Operations development process. The main objective of the data collection is to identify and analyze the main tasks needed to accomplish functions allocated to personnel, the information, controls, alarms, performance requirements and task support required to accomplish these tasks The interviews will be conducted virtually with MS Teams or another video conferencing tool depending on interviewee acceptance of the used tool. The interviews will be recorded if consent to do so is received from the interviewee.	Art. 6(1)(a): Consent : Voluntary participation based on informed consent for research or testing activities	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 2.2	Name, Surname, email address, phone number,	External stakeholders (Border	VTT will identify and recruit external stakeholders to	Art. 6(1)(a): Consent: Voluntary participation based	Yes (to non-EU partners

	<p>role within the organisation. Country of organisation in which the end user is employed, their organisation, and organisational unit</p>	<p>management authorities other than project partners, CSDP entities other than project partners)</p>	<p>conduct interviews to support elicitation of requirements. The main objective of the data collection is to extract the requirements for the technical system integrating and supporting end-user needs for the technologies, additional legacy systems, cyber-secure communication, and acceptability.</p> <p>The interviews will be conducted virtually with MS Teams or another video conferencing tool depending on interviewee acceptance of the used tool. The interviews will be recorded if consent to do so is received from the interviewee.</p>	<p>on informed consent for research or testing activities</p>	<p>within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)</p>
Task 2.5	<p>Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organisation. Country of organisation in which the end user is employed, their organisation, and organisational unit</p>	<p>External stakeholders (Border management authorities other than project partners, CSDP entities other than project partners)</p>	<p>Personal Data will be collected when conducting interviews with external stakeholders and literature review of societal and ethical values.</p>	<p>Art. 6(1)(a): Consent: Voluntary participation based on informed consent for research or testing activities</p>	<p>Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)</p>
Task 2.6	<p>Name, Surname, email address, phone number,</p>	<p>Consortium Partners</p>	<p>Personal data of BorderForce’s partners will be</p>	<p>Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract</p>	<p>Yes (to non-EU partners</p>

	role within the organisation.		collected in focus groups and interviews for scenario development. In relation to gathering information from stakeholders: no external partners to the project is foreseen to be included in the focus groups and interviews.	Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 3.1	Videos / Images	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Image data will be recorded in dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the Pilot Demonstrations) for developing computer vision algorithms (detection/tracking of vehicles, persons etc) and also processing image data in the final BorderForce system.	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for the technical development and validation of project deliverables under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 3.2	Full name, Username(s) or aliases, Date of birth, Gender, Nationality, Email addresses, Phone numbers, Physical addresses (if publicly shared), Social media handles, Social media posts, comments, and interactions, Profile bios and	Online Identities (The representation of a person, organisation, or entity within the digital realm (Clearnet and/or Darknet) indulging in <u>online activities</u>)	The processing of personal data by the OSINT tool will comply with local data protection laws (e.g., GDPR) and will be justifiable by the tool's configuration by the users.	Article 9(2)(j) the processing is strictly for scientific or statistical research with in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific	No

	<p>descriptions, Links shared or websites visited (if publicly referenced), IP addresses (if exposed in leaks or public logs), Timestamps of activity, Photos or videos uploaded, Text files, PDFs, or other documents shared publicly, Metadata from media (e.g., geolocation, device info), Friends, followers, or connections on social platforms, Mentions of family, colleagues, or acquaintances, Group memberships or affiliationsName, Surname, e-mail, images, videos</p>			<p>measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.</p>	
<p>Task 3.3</p>	<p>Videos / Images</p>	<p>Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners</p>	<p>Image data will be recorded in dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the Pilot Demonstrations) for developing computer vision algorithms (detection/tracking of vehicles, persons etc) and also processing image data in the final BorderForce system.</p>	<p>Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract: Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement</p>	<p>No</p>

Task 4.3	Videos / Images	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Video/ image data from dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the Pilot Demonstrations) will be processed for showing it to the end-users	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 4.4	Videos / Images	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Video/ image data from dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the Pilot Demonstrations) will be processed for showing it to the end-users	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 5.1	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organization, Videos / Images	Consortium Partners	Personal data of partners may be processed for the development of the roadmap which will describe the integration process and responsibilities of the project partners.	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract: Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 5.2	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organization, Videos / Images Analysed Testdata (Name, Surname, e-mail,	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Personal data will be processed of those participating in the testing site	Art. 6(1)(b) Necessary for system testing and validation activities under the Grant Agreement	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)

	organisation, images, videos)				
Task 5.3	Videos / Images	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Video/ image data from dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the Pilot Demonstrations) will be processed for showing it to the end-users during the training sessions	Art. 6(1)(b) Necessary for system testing and validation activities under the Grant Agreement	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 5.4	Data available from T5.1, T5.2, T5.3: Partner information (i.e. Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organization, images, videos) Analysed Testdata (Name, Surname, e-mail, organisation, images, videos)	BorderForce partners (tech provider, test supporters, end users) Processed, recorded test data Processed, prepared test data	Benchmarking the BorderForce System to document of lessons learned for operational environment.	Necessary for system testing and validation activities under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 6.1	names, contact details, images	Project Partners Target audiences, stakeholders and end users	Personal of project partners will be included where sharing the activities and outcomes, as well those included in content created on demonstrations. Personal data of target audiences, stakeholders and end users to promote the project's outcomes will be involved, specifically in	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement, with opt-out options	No

			relation to a mailing list.		
Task 6.2	names, contact details	Project Partners	Personal data of project partners involved in communications with standardisation activities	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 6.3	name and contact details etc	Advisory Board	Personal data of Advisory board will be collected for communication purposes	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 6.4	names and email addresses,	Project Partners	To establish commercial partnerships.	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for for responsible communication, and dissemination.	No
Task 7.1- T7.5	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organisation	Consortium Partners	For the purpose of communication, cooperation and information sharing between Consortium Partners.	Article 6(1)(b): performance of a contract: Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 8.1	Videos / Images Full name, Username(s) or aliases, Date of	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by	Image data will be recorded in dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract	No

	<p>birth, Gender, Nationality, Email addresses, Phone numbers, Physical addresses (if publicly shared), Social media handles, Social media posts, comments, and interactions, Profile bios and descriptions, Links shared or websites visited (if publicly referenced), IP addresses (if exposed in leaks or public logs), Timestamps of activity, Photos or videos uploaded, Text files, PDFs, or other documents shared publicly, Metadata from media (e.g., geolocation, device info), Friends, followers, or connections on social platforms, Mentions of family, colleagues, or acquaintances, Group memberships or affiliations Name, Surname, e-mail, images, videos</p>	<p>Consortium Partners</p> <p>Online Identities (The representation of a person, organisation, or entity within the digital realm (Clearnet and/or Darknet) indulging in <u>online activities</u>)</p>	<p>Pilot Demonstrations) for developing computer vision algorithms (detection/tracking of vehicles, persons etc) and also processing image data in the final BorderForce system.</p> <p>The processing of personal data by the OSINT tool will comply with local data protection laws (e.g., GDPR) and will be justifiable by the tool’s configuration by the users.</p>	<p>Necessary for the technical development and validation of project deliverables under the Grant Agreement</p>	
Task 8.2	Videos / Images	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by	Video/ image data from dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the Pilot Demonstrations) will	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract	No

		Consortium Partners	be processed for showing it to the end-users	Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	
Task 8.3	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organization, Videos / Images	Consortium Partners	Personal data of partners may be processed for the development of the roadmap which will describe the integration process and responsibilities of the project partners.	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract: Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 8.4	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organization, Videos / Images	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Personal data will be processed of those participating in the testing site	Art. 6(1)(b) Necessary for system testing and validation activities under the Grant Agreement	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 9.1	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organisation. Country of organisation in which the end user is employed, their organisation, and organisational unit Analysed Testdata (Name, Surname, e-mail, organisation, images, videos)	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Partner information of those participating in the testing site of BDI – simulating the operational environment from targeted real border locations	Art. 6(1)(b) Necessary for system testing and validation activities under the Grant Agreement	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 9.2	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by	Personal data of the end users (i.e. border guards and other personnel) that will	Art. 6(1)(b) and Art. 6(1)(c)	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium:

	<p>organisation. Country of organisation in which the end user is employed, their organisation, and organisational unit</p> <p>Analysed Testdata (Name, Surname, e-mail, organisation, images, videos)</p>	Consortium Partners	<p>interact with the system may be processed, in order to create accounts to log on to the system as well as to train the end users.</p> <p>Personal data of partners participating in trials will be collected for the purpose of issuing security clearances for entry into the trial’s premises.</p>	Necessary for system access under the Grant Agreement and for compliance with security regulations	Moldova, Albania)
Task 9.3	<p>Data available from T9.1, T9.2: Partner information (i.e. Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organization, images, videos)</p> <p>Analysed Testdata (Name, Surname, e-mail, organisation, images, videos)</p>	Consortium Partners & Personnel employed by Consortium Partners	Video/ image data from dedicated recording sessions (e.g. in the Pilot Demonstrations) will be processed for showing it to the end-users during the training sessions	Art. 6(1)(b) Necessary for validation tasks under the Grant Agreement	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 9.4	Name, Surname, email address, phone number, role within the organisation.		Personal data will be collected when conducting a literature research for ethics training / monitoring and demonstrations.	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract for ethics monitoring and training with appropriate safeguards	Yes (to non-EU partners within the Consortium: Moldova, Albania)
Task 10.1	names, contact details, images	Project Partners	Personal of project partners will be included where sharing the activities	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract for dissemination and stakeholder	No

		Target audiences, stakeholders and end users	and outcomes, as well those included in content created on demonstrations. Personal data of target audiences, stakeholders and end users to promote the project’s outcomes will be involved, specifically in relation to a mailing list.	engagement activities	
Task 10.2	names, contact details	Project Partners	Personal data of project partners involved in communications with standardisation activities	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of a contract Necessary for project coordination, technical development, or validation under the Grant Agreement	No
Task 10.3	name and contact details etc	Advisory Board	Personal data of Advisory board will be collected for communication purposes	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of contract for Advisory Board engagement and communication	No
Task 10.4	Names, emails, addressed & Analysed Testdata (Name, Surname, e-mail, organisation, images, videos)	Project Partners	To establish commercial partnerships.	Art. 6(1)(b): Performance of contract Necessary for commercial exploitation and impact assessment activities	No

Table 4 Personal data use in BorderForce

8 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPR) MANAGEMENT

All partners in the Consortium have agreed on explicit rules that need to be concerned as regards to the Intellectual Property (IP) ownership. In that way, access rights have been given to any Background and Foreground for the execution and protection of intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and confidential information before the project starts. All details have been addressed within the Consortium Agreement between all project partners and aligned with the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement (Articles 16).

8.1 Definitions

Intellectual Property Rights or IPR(s) means patents, patent applications and other statutory rights in inventions; copyrights (including without limitation copyrights in Software); registered design rights, applications for registered design rights, unregistered design rights and other statutory rights in designs; and other similar or equivalent forms of statutory protection, wherever in the world arising or available, but excluding rights in Classified Information and/or trade secrets.

Background means any data, know-how or information – whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that:

- is held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Consortium Agreement, and
- is needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

Foreground or Result(s) means any tangible or intangible output of the Project, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the Project as well as any rights attached to them, including intellectual property rights.

8.1.1 Applicable legislation

- European Patent Convention, 16th edition⁹ (published June 2016) which contains the Convention on the Grant of European Patents (EPC) as in force since 13 December 2007, the EPC Implementing Regulations as in force since 1 May 2016 but also including an amendment that entered into force on 1 November 2016, the rules of procedure of the EPO boards of appeal and Enlarged Board of Appeal, included for the first time in an edition of the EPC, the protocols forming integral parts of the EPC (Protocol on the Interpretation of Article 69 EPC, Protocol on Centralisation, Protocol on Recognition, Protocol on Privileges and Immunities, Protocol on the Staff Complement), an extract from the EPC Revision Act of 29 November 2000, the Administrative Council's decision of 28 June 2001 on the transitional provisions under Article 7 of the Revision Act, and the Rules relating to Fees.
- Regulation (EU) 2017/1001¹⁰ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2017 on the European Union trademark.
- Council Regulation (EC) No 6/2002¹¹ of 12 December 2001 on Community designs.
- Directive (EU) 2019/790¹² of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC (Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market).

- Directive 2001/29/EC13 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society.
- Directive 96/9/EC14 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases.
- Directive 2009/24/EC15 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs.
- Directive 2004/48/EC16 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights.
- National laws on patent, design, trademark and copyright protection.

8.2 IPR Management in the BorderForce Project

The BorderForce Consortium Agreement expressly stipulates the rules related to the management of IP rights and distinguishes, on the one hand, the IP rights that are held by the partners prior to their accession in the Consortium Agreement and are needed for the Project (Background) and, on the other hand, the IP rights that are held by the partners during the lifetime of the Project (Results).

In particular, Section 8 Results and Section 9 Access Rights of the BorderForce Consortium Agreement include all relevant clauses that have been agreed between the partners and refer to the IPR management. In Attachment 1 of the BorderForce Consortium Agreement, the Parties have identified and agreed on the Background for the Project and have also, where relevant, informed each other that access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits. Therefore, we aim to work methodically in order to classify BorderForce IPRs and define:

- the treatment of existing IPRs (background),
- the management of joint ownership. Partners will keep record of their contributions which are protected by IP Law and potentially Trade Secrets. This will permit the Consortium to discern the share of each owner in relation to the results of a joint effort. BorderForce Partners aim to reach a point where exploitation of results will become possible,
- the protection and management of the results of BorderForce (foreground),
- the exploitation and dissemination of the results of BORDERFORCE (foreground),
- the protection of know how created during BorderForce.

Furthermore, section 4 and section 5 of the BorderForce Consortium Agreement provide for the responsibilities of the partners and their liability towards each other (including for the management of IP rights).

All partners may settle any disputes in accordance with the clause 11.8 of the BorderForce Consortium Agreement.

To effectively achieve the aforementioned objectives regarding the overall management of IPRs, a cumulative IPR Control form will be circulated by the coordinator.

9 ETHICAL ASPECTS

The BorderForce project acknowledges that ethics play a critical role in ensuring that its research and technological development activities uphold fundamental rights, human dignity, and responsible innovation. Ethics considerations are embedded across multiple work packages and tasks, with dedicated attention given in Tasks 1.5, 2.5, 7.5, and 9.4, and their corresponding deliverables (D1.3, D2.4, D7.1, and D9.2).

These tasks address the ethical requirements established by the European Commission (EC) during the ethics review process that preceded the signature of the Grant Agreement. They guide the consortium in aligning project activities with EU legal and ethical frameworks, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Horizon Europe, AI Act, and relevant international human rights standards.

In cases where the consortium collects data directly from people, it will ensure that informed consent is obtained in a meaningful and transparent way. Participants are clearly informed about what data is being collected, for what purpose, and how their rights will be respected throughout. This applies to activities such as workshops, interviews, system testing, and field trials. Consent forms are reviewed centrally and adapted to the needs of each task, with support from the ethics lead.

Following the principle of data minimisation, BorderForce only collect what is strictly necessary to meet the task's objectives. This is particularly important in work involving video recordings, open-source social media data, or user interaction during field simulations. Wherever possible, the consortium will rely on pseudonymisation or aggregation to reduce identifiability. In cases where full anonymisation is not possible, such as small expert groups, we apply strict access controls and limit data use to within the consortium.

BorderForce is aware that certain tasks, especially those using OSINT tools or simulating sensitive border operations, may carry higher ethical risks. To address these, the consortium will ensure that OSINT tools only access publicly available information and are not configured to profile individuals without explicit justification. No personal data is collected covertly or from closed environments, and avoid targeting vulnerable groups. In addition to GDPR compliance, the project commits to respecting the Terms of Service and usage policies of any platforms from which publicly available information is accessed through OSINT tools (e.g., TikTok, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube). Automated access to public data will only occur where it is permissible by the platforms' terms, ensuring that the project does not breach contractual obligations. Although BorderForce does not directly target vulnerable groups, the project will implement a mechanism to monitor indirect impacts on marginalised populations during field activities and OSINT operations. Any concerns arising will be documented and addressed through the project's ethics oversight process.

Access to all sensitive data is secured using authentication protocols and role-based permissions. BorderForce will ensure that only authorised individuals can access identifiable information. Retention periods are defined per dataset and reviewed to make sure data isn't kept longer than necessary.

Eticas (EDS) leads ethics activities, offering guidance across the consortium and supporting partners in ethical risk assessments, and compliance with data protection standards. Ethics training and regular monitoring help us stay responsive to evolving ethical challenges and ensure that all partners have the tools and understanding they need to meet their obligations. All of these efforts are guided by GDPR compliance, national legislation, and the ethical standards set out under Horizon Europe. In this way, the project builds ethics into the design of its data processes, rather than treating it as an afterthought.

10 CONCLUSIONS

The present deliverable constitutes the Project Data Management Plan at Month 6 of the project. As such, the present deliverable must be intended as a guideline with respect to data management, reporting the main principles that BorderForce project is adherent to and providing a snapshot on the implications of Security and Ethics on data management.

